

GOVERNING WIND ENERGY TOGETHER

POLICY BRIEF

OCTOBER 2025

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Lead authors (in alphabetical order):

Lien Bakelants, Monika Bucha, Marta Cecconi, Dominik Huber, Rebecca Hueting, Bozhidar Ivanov, Jann Launer, Alena Lohrmann, Cristina Madrid-Lopez, Filipe Moreira Alves, Maeva Lavigne Philippot, Luis Ramirez Camargo, Amanda Schibline, Stéphanie van de Raad, Guillermo Valenzuela, Julia Wittmayer.

Contributing authors (in alphabetical order):

Peter Burgherr, Andrzej Ceglaz, Josie Coburn, Thomas Fransen, Andrea Noemi Hahmann, Sabine Hielscher, Russell McKenna, Christian Mikovits, Jens Lowitzsch, Evangelos Panos, Kristian Petrick, Stefan Pfenninger, James Price, Gerald Putra, Thomas Schauppenlehner, Miquel Sierra-Montoya, Andrew Stirling, Teun Strikker, Iva Tajnsek, Mariya Trifonova, Marianne Zeyringer.

Project coordination:

JustWind4All: Julia Wittmayer (DRIFT)
WIMBY: Luis Ramirez Camargo (Utrecht University)

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EXEC UTIVE SUM MARY

The JustWind4All and WIMBY projects were launched in 2022 and 2023 with a shared mission: to accelerate wind energy deployment in Europe in ways that are both socially just and environmentally responsible. Over almost three years, through transdisciplinary co-production, advanced modelling, qualitative research and innovative participatory tools, the projects explored how wind can be deployed faster while strengthening democracy and justice. JustWind4All and WIMBY joined forces to tackle a critical question for Europe's energy transition: how can we accelerate wind deployment in a way that is both just and effective?

While JustWind4All brought together energy systems modelling, holistic impact assessment and participatory governance in regional Wind Labs, WIMBY took a hands-on approach to mitigating the "Not in My Back Yard" (NIMBY) effect: developing engaging, participatory tools to foster citizen involvement in wind planning. Together, they engaged municipalities, regional planners, energy communities, NGOs, wind power developers, industry and policymakers across diverse regional contexts, co-creating resources to inform planning and decision-making at multiple scales.

This Policy Brief presents six interlinked "how-to" areas, each reflecting insights and recommendations drawn from our work. Taken together, they show that accelerating wind is not just about installing turbines, but about embedding justice, trustworthiness, and transparency at every stage of the process while considering uncertainties and trade-offs.

1. Holistic assessment

The EU's wind expansion ambition requires clearer tools to navigate the socio-ecological trade-offs that remain poorly defined in current planning. Standardising a holistic assessment that accounts for global impact displacement, delayed benefits, regional inequalities, and biodiversity-sensitive siting would provide a stronger basis for realistic deployment targets, zoning decisions, and public support.

2. Holistic energy system modelling

Integrating social and environmental considerations into energy system modelling is essential to guide Europe's wind deployment in ways that are cost-effective, publicly acceptable, and ecologically responsible. By linking macro-scale and micro-scale models, policymakers can better visualise trade-offs, align national targets with local sensitivities, and foster more transparent, inclusive decision-making.

3. Participation in decision-making

Inclusive participation that 'opens up' policy challenges is about more than ticking consultation boxes. It requires early, continuous, and locally tailored involvement that recognises past injustices, highlights (rather than obscures) divergences and gives citizens real influence over outcomes.

4. Financial participation

A just transition must also be a fair transition. Citizens should share in the economic benefits of wind projects, through mandatory frameworks for compensation, co-ownership, and innovative models that include vulnerable households.

5. Modelling, open data & transparency

Reliable, accessible data and transparent models are a foundation of trustworthiness in planning. Without harmonised data infrastructures and user-friendly visualisations, decisions risk opacity and public scepticism.

6. Untapped resources (airborne, floating, repowering)

Europe's wind future will depend on innovation as well as expansion. Emerging technologies and repowering strategies offer new opportunities for scaling wind while minimising land-use pressures and strengthening community acceptance.

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Across these six dimensions, our findings underline a simple but powerful message: accelerating wind deployment in Europe requires more than compliance with EU permitting deadlines or Renewable Energy Directive (RED) targets. It calls for diagnostic approaches that ask not just whether processes exist, but whether they work in ways that are ecologically sound, socially just and overall effective.

Our guidance is intended to support EU, national, and local policymakers in translating European targets of achieving at least 42.5% of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in gross final energy consumption by 2030 (with the ambition of achieving 45%) and related instruments (like RED III's Renewables Acceleration Areas) into just, locally embedded, trustworthy and effective pathways for wind energy deployment.

1

Holistic assessment

CONTEXT / CHALLENGE

The EU plans to double its wind power capacity within five years but faces the challenge of navigating complex social and environmental landscapes. To inform these decisions, the recommendation is to perform a holistic assessment. However, in JustWind4All, we found that the literature is disjointed and that there is a lack of a clear definition of what a holistic assessment is. Because of this gap, issues like global impacts, material dependencies, or the A definition of holistic assessment that considers the interconnected socio-ecological aspects of wind power would provide a clearer picture of these trade-offs, serving as a better foundation for identifying priority areas and no-go zones. It would also help in setting realistic targets for energy sovereignty and domestic technology manufacturing.

In societal discourse, wind energy is regularly criticised for not being as environmentally friendly as promoted, especially when considering location-specific data and framed as a considerable source of biodiversity losses, in particular for birds. In this regard, the WIMBY project developed a life cycle assessment model based on geographically refined life cycle inventory modelling and assessed biodiversity impacts due to land use changes based on satellite data. Thus, it complements the holistic assessment of wind energy.

INSIGHTS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Environmental impacts are globally redistributed, not eliminated

The JustWind4All project's distinction between onsite and offsite impacts reveals how decarbonization can shift environmental burdens from Europe to manufacturing and resource-exporting countries.

A wind-based energy transition in Europe will take time to yield tangible socio-ecological benefits

While most energy models assume a decarbonised manufacturing sector, the reality is that the infrastructure required for this transition will primarily be built using today's fossil-heavy energy mix. In Spain, for instance, the breakeven point for reducing climate change impacts is approximately 9.5 years. However, for other environmental categories—such as marine eutrophication (24.3 years), water use (10 years), and mainly material resource depletion (over 1,200 years)—the benefits are either significantly delayed or potentially unattainable.

Regional disparities in environmental burdens may worsen distributional injustice

Not all regions experience the impacts of wind installations equally. This is due to local installations, wind blade cemeteries, or component manufacturing, which is also concentrated in space, creating impact hotspots and increasing local resistance. The Spanish case in JustWind4All demonstrated how improvements in environmental indicators at the national level can hide regional inequalities. Some autonomous communities benefit from reduced impacts due to the phase-out of fossil fuels, while others face increased pressures from biomass or infrastructure expansion.

Whereas intensive impact indicators are heavily dependent on the electricity yield, total impacts are based on material demands and location. Intensive indicators based in yield by KWh or MW are detached from location-specific factors such as transport, connection cables, or foundations. When impacts are expressed per unit of generated electricity, these regionalised components and

1. HOLISTIC ASSESSMENT

activities contribute only 12–16% of the total effects. In contrast, absolute differences in impacts are primarily driven by physical flows, such as material demands and the location of the infrastructure.

Biodiversity impacts are higher in natural areas. The WIMBY project found that the bigger the direct

change in surface area, the higher the impact on biodiversity. Building wind turbines on natural land and not on agricultural land should not be recommended considering the larger impact it has. Transformed areas, such as industrial polygons or industrialized agricultural land should be prioritised to limit biodiversity impacts.

Figure 1: Change in regional environmental impact intensity (per kWh) from 2024 to 2030.

1. HOLISTIC ASSESSMENT

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RECOMMENDATIONS

Define and standardise holistic assessment across the EU

A shared definition is essential to guide wind energy planning under the REPowerEU plan, the Renewable Energy Directive, and the European Wind Power Action Plan. Holistic assessment should include at least Socio-ecological trade-offs (e.g., land use vs. biodiversity), Global impact displacement (e.g., upstream emissions and resource extraction), and Regional inequalities (e.g., uneven distribution of infrastructure and burdens). This would support more sustainable zoning decisions, help identify priority areas and no-go zones, and align with EU strategic autonomy goals under the Net-Zero Industry Act.

Include global impacts in energy planning tools

With global supply chains, production of wind turbines may shift environmental burdens upstream to extraction and manufacturing stages, often outside the EU. Planning tools like JRC's POTEnCIA model and NECP templates must be updated to reflect these global impacts. This would prevent externalizing harm and ensure alignment with the EU Green Deal, UN SDGs, and the Environmental Footprint method promoted by the European Commission.

Adjust deployment targets to reflect delayed benefits

Wind infrastructure built today relies on fossil-heavy inputs. While climate benefits may materialise in a few years, others may take too long. Deployment targets under REPowerEU and 2030 Climate Target Plan should reflect these timelines and integrate life-cycle thinking to avoid misleading short-term gains.

Address regional disparities in public engagement and zoning

National-level improvements can mask regional hotspots of environmental pressure, fueling local resistance. EU instruments like the Just Transition Mechanism, Cohesion Policy, and Energy Communities frameworks should be leveraged to promote territorially sensitive planning, especially in regions hosting wind infrastructure, component manufacturing, or end-of-life facilities like blade cemeteries.

Strengthen biodiversity-sensitive siting criteria

It is recognised that land use change is globally the main driver of biodiversity loss. Therefore, EU frameworks such as the Renewable Energy Directive, REPowerEU, and the European Wind Power Action Plan should adjust siting guidelines. For instance those guidelines could highlight the need for reduced surface change area and prioritise agricultural or degraded land over natural habitats, integrate ecoregion-specific sensitivity into zoning tools, and strengthen biodiversity safeguards under the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

2

Holistic energy system modelling

CONTEXT / CHALLENGE

Despite the anticipated role of wind energy in achieving net-zero targets, its deployment is increasingly facing local opposition and environmental challenges. These challenges include the potential impacts of wind development on, for example, landscape aesthetics, human well-being (i.e., due to noise or shadow flicker), and wildlife. It is imperative to understand how various social and environmental impacts may affect wind siting, energy system costs, and energy mix across Europe. Our projects addressed a critical challenge of Europe's energy system transition: integrating high shares of wind into the energy system while balancing social acceptance and environmental prioritisation.

WIMBY developed a novel modelling framework linking two continental scale energy system models (highRES-Europe and JRC-EU-TIMES), and a micro-scale wind farm model to explore the trade-offs between wind energy deployment, system costs, and societal and environmental impacts. Similarly, JustWind4All has developed a modelling method that produces techno-economically feasible energy system designs on a continental level, and based on that, consistent designs at higher resolution for countries or regions. Our findings underscore the need for nuanced, location-specific planning that considers not just technical potential but also social and environmental protection. Our approach enables policymakers to visualise and quantify these trade-offs, supporting more informed, transparent, and inclusive decision-making.

INSIGHTS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Social and environmental considerations should guide a more integrative approach to wind energy deployment in Europe

In scenarios that prioritise environmental and social protection by excluding especially sensitive locations, onshore wind capacity may be more limited – potentially up to 85% less by 2050 compared to a scenario with less restrictive constraints. Even under these scenarios, wind and

solar continue to form the backbone of Europe's electricity generation in 2050, reinforcing their role as low-regret options in diverse planning contexts.

Increased wind deployment reduces energy system costs and shifts technology mix

When land availability for onshore wind is less restricted, Europe can achieve a more cost-effective energy transition – reducing overall energy system costs by up to 15%. This enables a more balanced and efficient technology mix, easing reliance on offshore wind, solar PV, and nuclear, and supporting faster progress toward 2050 climate targets.

Micro-scale planning reveals hidden costs in macro models

Internal and external cabling costs, which vary significantly by location, can substantially impact project economics but are typically not captured in high-level energy system models, highlighting the value of detailed, site-specific planning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Integrate social and ecological constraints into national, regional and local energy planning procedures and tools

Governments and planning agencies should increase their use of spatially explicit models that account for factors besides cost, such as local biodiversity, landscape, and population sensitivities when setting regionally-tailored renewable energy targets.

Use models to foster transparent communication and inclusive public dialogue on energy choices

Governments and institutions should actively engage the public in open discussions about the benefits and trade-offs of all energy technologies. Transparent communication and inclusive dialogue are essential to building

2. HOLISTIC ENERGY SYSTEM MODELLING

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trustworthiness, achieving societal consensus, and navigating complex decisions in the energy transition.

Models that show trade-offs between different possible scenarios and quantify the effect of choices, for example the added cost by excluding certain areas from wind development – can help this process.

Incorporate micro-scale spatial and economic analysis into planning and permitting processes

Local authorities should use high-resolution tools to evaluate trade-offs between energy output and infrastructure costs before approving wind projects.

Figure 2: Land availability (upper panel) and spatial distribution of onshore wind capacities on NUTS2 level (lower panel) for the three levels of social and environmental protection: low, medium and high. Social protection excludes zones around residential areas (due to noise, shadow flicker) as well as high scenic landscapes. Environmental protection restricts wind deployment in nature protected sites, for instance, under the Birds and the Habitats Directives. Lower protection scenario concentrates wind in high-yield regions, while higher protection scenario reduces total capacity and distributes it more evenly across NUTS2 areas.

3

Participation in decision-making

CONTEXT / CHALLENGE

While the acceleration of wind energy development is one way to increase renewable based energy production, it does come with impacts for the environment and the local population. Listening to, involving and engaging with the local population in the development of wind energy is therefore crucial. There are diverse participatory practices in wind energy – including information sharing, public consultation or advisory panels. However, those participatory practices, when actually used, often seem to fall short in terms of inclusivity, empowerment or transparency. They also rarely address contextual issues such as structural inequalities or historical injustices. This can result in unequal access to decision-making, like where wind turbines are placed or how networks are expanded, and can make the process vulnerable to special interests influencing participation. Therefore, citizens may express dissatisfaction with how wind energy is being developed through protests or by mobilizing counter expertise. Considering protest as valuable assessments rather than as nuisance opens up possibilities for more inclusive and informed decision-making in wind energy projects. Additionally, tensions between national and local governance can make public participation challenging, as local authorities work to represent community interests while navigating national targets and regulations.

INSIGHTS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Underlying structural inequalities and historical injustices may persist in wind energy development

Wind energy developments are shaped by regional histories and governance structures and have faced shifting dynamics over time, with early top-down projects often triggering resistance. While this led to new governance approaches, in some areas, these efforts came too late to rebuild trustworthiness, underscoring the need for more proactive governance. As such these historical injustices still influence both the

speed with which wind energy can be developed and the social outcomes thereof. In economically and politically weaker regions, such as Brandenburg, Germany, external investors have primarily benefited from wind energy, while local communities have only recently seen initiatives for cooperative ownership. Similarly, in North Holland, The Netherlands, offshore wind expansion has shifted the burden away from onshore communities, raising concerns about whose interests are prioritised.

Not all participatory practices contribute to inclusivity, empowerment and transparency

Based on over 300 case studies globally, a key conclusion is that despite the rise in wind energy projects, opportunities for meaningful participation remain limited. The complexity of these projects can make it difficult for citizens to engage without adequate support and information. Legal frameworks often focus on formal consultation processes, which do not guarantee genuine stakeholder impact on decision-making. When treated as procedural formalities rather than genuine efforts to involve citizens, people may feel heard but not considered, which together with a lack of transparency in decision-making can lead to untrustworthiness – and thus distrust and scepticism. This is particularly the case when participatory processes try to force agreement and, in doing so, hide genuine differences of perspectives. Additionally, the quality and scope of participatory practices varies significantly between wind energy projects, leaving many communities feeling marginalised, uninformed, or powerless to influence outcomes.

Social innovation initiatives provide promising participatory practices

While many larger-sized, top-down organised wind energy projects more easily lead to social opposition, wind energy projects driven by social innovation initiatives engage in more inclusive and transparent participatory

3. PARTICIPATION IN DECISION-MAKING

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practices. These initiatives involve civil society and third-sector organizations, and examples include municipalities collaborating with citizen associations, energy cooperatives, community development trusts, and Indigenous communities pursuing energy autonomy through grassroots projects. Despite also addressing gender equality and energy poverty, these alternatives often lack support and face legal and financial hurdles. Overall, while cooperatives offer more inclusive participation they tend to invest mainly in small-scale projects.

Responsibilities of different governance levels are blurred, hindering legitimacy and accountability

National governments in the EU have set ambitious wind energy expansion targets, but local and regional authorities often face challenges in implementing them. This misalignment between national acceleration policies and local execution leads to bottlenecks and delays. Local authorities frequently lack the necessary resources, such as personnel, to effectively manage these projects. For example, in Brandenburg, Germany, municipalities encounter feasibility concerns and workforce shortages, while smaller municipalities in North Holland, The Netherlands, struggle with participatory planning demands under the renewable energy strategy framework. These issues stem from different interests and capabilities, and hiding these differences can lead to untrustworthiness—ultimately fuelling stronger resistance to wind energy projects.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Implement inclusive participation models at all stages of wind development

Involve citizens living near wind farms from the earliest planning stage through construction, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning.

Processes should acknowledge social, economic, and environmental impacts, address past injustices or conflicts around wind energy development, and openly highlight — rather than hide — differences of perspectives. Without this openness, untrustworthiness of earlier projects is likely to carry over into new ones.

No one-size-fits-all: anchor inclusive participation locally

When designing and implementing a participatory process, carefully consider different aspects of participation — such as the level of participation, the model or practice of participation, target groups, and continuity — and tailor it to local history, needs, and actor networks related to wind energy development.

Provide framework conditions allowing for more inclusive participation in wind project development

Design policies and regulatory frameworks that enable social innovation initiatives, allowing direct citizen participation in co-financing and managing wind energy projects. These should focus on public financing schemes or provide financial security to support social innovation initiatives, especially when transitioning from pilot and prototype phases to actual implementation.

Coordinate and align interests, capacities, resources, and responsibilities between governance levels

Establish clear frameworks that harmonise national policy with regional implementation and local democratic processes, providing necessary resources. Such harmonization prevents municipalities from experiencing bottlenecks or becoming scapegoats, while also considering different and evolving justice issues.

4

Financial participation

CONTEXT / CHALLENGE

While one way to integrate energy justice considerations in wind energy development is by attending to procedural aspects such as inclusive participation and decision making processes, a similarly important aspect relates to the distribution of economic benefits accruing from wind energy development. While financial participation is central to energy justice, there are deep regulatory asymmetries across European states. Some states actively mandate citizen participation and co-ownership in energy communities while others have outdated or restrictive legal frameworks, and regulatory gaps that lock citizens out of these opportunities. These disparities result in injustices: some communities benefit directly, while others bear burdens without rewards. Often vulnerable households remain largely excluded from participation, deepening inequality. Attention to energy justice therefore requires a shift toward distributing costs and benefits of wind energy investments more equitably among all affected stakeholders.

INSIGHTS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Most European countries have binding laws on financial participation and compensation

The usage of financial participation and compensation schemes differs strongly between (and within) European countries. Illustrated in figure 3, light green countries encourage developers to compensate affected regions or residents indirectly. Medium green countries promote direct financial participation and investment opportunities. Dark green countries promote and regulate co-ownership and economic participation of local stakeholders. These varied approaches translate directly into uneven levels of energy justice: the strength of legislation often determines whether local communities become active beneficiaries of the energy transition or remain passive bystanders bearing its burdens.

Municipal compensation schemes promote local sustainability and democratic control if well executed

In many countries, national or local governments require wind park operators to make financial contributions to host municipalities. Ideally, these funds are administered by residents living near the wind farm who democratically decide on their use. In practice, however, the funds are often allocated to initiatives that enhance sustainability and local well-being, such as home insulation for low-income households, or support for local associations. Over time and without transparent governance or citizen involvement, such funds risk becoming opaque budgetary inflows rather than delivering equitable benefits.

Citizen investments are possible, but rarely mandated or realised

In several countries (e.g. Belgium, Poland, Spain), regulations allow that wind park operators offer project shares to citizens through mechanisms, such as crowdlending or cooperative ownership, to keep financial returns within the local community. Yet, when such provisions are not legally binding, they rarely translate into practice and are being ignored or bypassed by private developers for not aligning with their commercial interests. In Portugal, for example, the option exists on paper but has never been implemented in practice.

4. FINANCIAL PARTICIPATION

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Financial barriers exclude vulnerable households - but inclusive models exist

No European country has formally addressed the barrier of - or proposed legal mechanisms to overcome - the exclusion of vulnerable households from acquiring shares in wind

energy projects. However, the Netherlands, in collaboration with citizen associations, provides non-binding guidelines promoting inclusive financing –among them, the solidarity principle, whereby governments purchase project shares and redistribute the returns to low-income or energy-poor households.

- No benefits / No economic participation
- Indirect benefits via compensation mechanisms
- Direct benefits and / or investment opportunities
- Co-ownership and governance rights

Figure 3: Financial Participation and Compensation Mechanisms in the EU27 + NO, CH and the UK

4. FINANCIAL PARTICIPATION

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RECOMMENDATIONS

Establish binding national legal frameworks for financial participation and compensation

Countries currently lacking regulation should adopt legally binding schemes to ensure fair benefit-sharing. These laws should explicitly address distributional justice and address structural injustices e.g. along gender or socio-economic dimensions.

Develop an EU-wide ‘justice catalogue’ for financial participation and compensation mechanisms

The European Commission should publish a comprehensive guideline – a justice catalogue – outlining the advantages and limitations of various financial participation and compensation schemes. Such a tool would support harmonisation across Member States, help prevent competitive distortions, and mitigate perceptions of unfair treatment between neighbouring regions.

Mandate transparent, community-led governance of municipal compensation funds

When opting for compensation payments to municipalities, these should be democratically governed by local communities. Citizens must be involved in deciding how funds are used to ensure alignment with local needs and to strengthen both procedural and distributional justice.

Introduce inclusive financing tools to enable participation by vulnerable households

Governments should adopt mechanisms enabling public actors to acquire and manage project shares on behalf of low-income households (such as the solidarity principle, The Netherlands). Financial and energy literacy programmes should accompany these measures to ensure informed participation.

Move from voluntary to mandatory citizen shareholding mechanisms

National laws should mandate citizen shareholding to promote social acceptance of renewable energy projects and ensure profits remain local. These instruments should be tailored to local contexts, recognising that their impact on justice outcomes varies depending on geographic and social conditions.

Strengthen legal clarity and close loopholes to prevent regulatory capture by corporate actors

Vague or optional provisions in EU and national law can serve as entry points for corporate interests to dilute justice-oriented goals. Policymakers should ensure that directives and national laws are precise and enforceable to prevent misuse and safeguard community interests.

5

Modelling, open data & transparency

CONTEXT / CHALLENGE

Transparent and accessible modelling and data are prerequisites for trustworthiness in wind planning, from local siting decisions to EU-wide energy scenarios. Effective planning depends on robust modelling and impact assessments that range from single projects to continental-scale scenarios. Our projects contribute to energy system modelling, life cycle assessment and holistic impact modelling across these levels. However, progress is hampered by issues of data availability and accountability, since models need input datasets with high spatial and temporal resolution that are often unavailable, restricted by licences, unclear in origin, hard to find, or difficult to process due to changing file formats and data schemas. Transparency is central to trustworthiness challenges, as tools are often expert-focused, behind paywalls, dispersed, and difficult to verify independently, while assessments produced by companies seeking to develop wind farms may lead to lack of trustworthiness. Moreover, even when data is available, transparent and trustworthy it might have intrinsic uncertainty that is inherited by the studies that are performed with it. Finally, understandability remains a barrier because non-experts struggle with the background and findings of models, literacy and information levels vary widely across stakeholders, and differing needs for modelling results make diverse feedback and prioritisation of functionality essential.

INSIGHTS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Development of data modules around wind power integration and its impacts on society and the environment

Both projects have developed data modules, each of them covering different aspects of wind power and its impacts, among others: area potentials, capacity factors, birds and bats collision risks and mortality, climate change

impacts, legislation and financial compensation, accidents, and scenic value. Our data modules produce input data for assessment tools and energy models and are ready to work standalone or be integrated into a larger modelling workflow.

Transparent and trustworthy data

Beyond filling crucial data gaps, our data modules support the goals of transparency, trustworthiness and understandability by allowing users to choose, customize, understand and thereby justifiably build trust in each dataset they use. Our data, and all the methods to construct them are thoroughly documented in deliverables, code repositories, scientific papers and summaries for non-experts.

Making expert data accessible and understandable for virtually everyone

Apart from classical dissemination channels (e.g. scientific publications and reports), WIMBY has developed tools that make expert knowledge and assessments available to a non-expert public. The 3D immersive platform (workshops) can be customized to needs of individual projects and regions across the continent and the WIMBY interactive map and forum is available and useful for any interested audience with an internet connection. Moreover, the team of WIMBY's 3D immersive platform has invested considerable effort in making the entire activity understandable for a wide range of stakeholders and in customizing storylines for each case study so that participants found accurate and detailed information about each of their regions. The game allowed participants to get a better understanding of wind power deployment and its impacts and the visualizations showed in a very concrete way how the local landscape would change. The feedback from participants has been very positive.

5. MODELLING, OPEN DATA & TRANSPARENCY

The iterative development process of the WIMBY interactive map and forum (Screenshot example in Figure 4) has meant that the functionality and visualization options have been continuously improved based on feedback from hundreds of users along the way. In the future, we will have to look for resources to keep data up-to-date and to continue developing the interface to the evolving needs of the target audiences and potential new users. In order to make an impact from the final project result, we should see it as a continuous, evolving process and not as a completed deliverable available online.

Data quality significantly affects uncertainty in modelling

Due to the complex mix of model semantics, resolution, data quality, and age, results can vary considerably—posing high risks if not accounted for. In JustWind4All, we found that in the Bulgarian NECP scenario with additional measures and higher share of wind resulted not only in lower impacts but also in lower uncertainty than the one without these measures.

Figure 4: WIMBY interactive map planning mode: Land use change, birds collision risk and LCA for a wind farm with 8 planned wind turbines.

5. MODELLING, OPEN DATA & TRANSPARENCY

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RECOMMENDATIONS

Invest in harmonised EU data infrastructures and cross-sectoral modelling tools as foundational elements for future wind energy strategies in Europe

Investment is needed in coordinated data collection and standardisation across Europe. Integrate and expand environmental and socio-economic datasets, including citizen perception and local governance data. For example, to improve transparency in turbine lifecycle data, investment should be prioritised to make key proprietary data, such as LCA inventories, open access. This is critical for accelerating research to better understand the holistic impacts of wind power deployment.

Provide long-term funding for maintenance and updates of data sets and modelling tools

Clear strategies and available monetary and personal resources ensure reliability by maintaining data sets and tools available in a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) way to stakeholders. This not only minimises administrative burden but also facilitates research and deployment in the wind power industry.

Support user-friendly visualisation tools and initiatives

Support user-friendly visualisation tools and initiatives that translate complex research results, such as data and models, into transparent, understandable and accessible insights for the non-specialised public: To build the trustworthiness of model-based research findings, we need to make sure that all assumptions can be understood and contested. Developing fully reproducible research takes considerable effort that should be acknowledged and supported. Making such data and models understandable for a wider public is even more demanding. Prioritising reproducibility and transparency and making funding available for such efforts will contribute to raise acceptance of science supported policy.

Address data uncertainty in decision-making and public engagement

Data uncertainty must be explicitly addressed. Under frameworks like REPowerEU and the NECPs, integrating uncertainty metrics into scenario tools and reporting can improve transparency and credibility. To support public engagement, uncertainty should not only be disclosed but also visually mapped
— highlighting where data is robust and where it is less reliable. This can help communities better understand trade-offs and risks.

6

Untapped resources: airborne, floating, repowering

CONTEXT / CHALLENGE

Conventional onshore and offshore wind remain central, but Europe must diversify its portfolio to meet decarbonisation goals. Repowering, floating offshore wind, and airborne wind energy (AWE) can expand capacity while easing land-use pressures and unlocking new opportunities. Yet, policy frameworks, permitting, and support measures lag behind technological potential.

Repowering

Repowering is the replacement of old wind turbines at the end of their lifetime with modern turbines. Repowering solutions can lower land use demand while increasing capacity, especially in already well-developed wind energy areas such as Germany, the UK, or Spain.

Floating offshore wind technology

Floating offshore wind technology involves placing wind turbines on floating platforms in deep waters, allowing access to wind resources beyond shallow seabeds where conventional offshore wind is not economically viable. This approach also reduces pressure on land use. It is especially relevant in countries where offshore wind is still emerging and coastal zones are already heavily used for activities such as tourism, fisheries, and maritime transport—for example, Portugal, France, Greece, Romania, and Bulgaria.

Airborne wind energy (AWE)

This is an innovative renewable energy technology that harnesses winds at high altitudes by using tethered kites or drones requiring less material input than other wind technologies.

INSIGHTS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Overall, expanding the use of repowering, offshore floating wind and airborne wind energy can generate additional capacity in the European energy network, contribute to Europe's decarbonisation strategy, decrease land use pressure, and provide site-specific solutions for densely utilised coastal areas and sites with strong wind shear.

Repowering existing turbines

So far, repowering is discussed as a strategy with substantial potential but has not been widely adopted yet. In the coming years, there will be significant potential for repowering in Europe, most prominently in countries that started to deploy wind turbines early such as Germany and Portugal. The JustWind4All analysis shows that by 2050, repowering the existing European wind fleet could deliver up to 260 GW of additional wind capacity, without any additional land use requirements. Delivering on this potential could be limited by the complex permitting process and regulatory barriers limiting uptake.

Offshore floating wind

Europe leads globally in floating wind, with ~195 MW already installed in several pioneering countries and more than 10 GW expected by 2030, supported by national targets and auctions. By 2050, deployment could exceed 250 GW, especially in countries with deep coastal waters such as Spain, Portugal, Ireland, Italy, Greece, France, Norway, and parts of the Black Sea, potentially meeting up to 30% of Europe's electricity demand under full decarbonization. Existing projects have shown how floating wind can contribute to hybrid decarbonisation, is commercially viable in harsh offshore environments, achieves competitive auction prices, and demonstrates long-term capacity in deep-water coastal contexts.

6. UNTAPPED RESOURCES: AIRBORNE, FLOATING, REPOWERING

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Airborne wind energy (AWE)

There are about ten AWE technology developers in Europe of which 2-3 have or are close to having commercial systems in the 100 kW range available (TRL 6-8); others have pilot or demonstration projects with TRL 4-5. There are some 10 test sites in Europe. While AWE is acknowledged in some policy documents and even some legislation (e.g. the German Renewable Energy Act EEG), AWE-specific policies and regulation are still lacking. AWE could become cost-competitive by the early 2030s and provide unique system benefits due to higher capacity factors and distinct generation patterns. Our results show that AWE could become the preferred wind technology at locations with high wind shear (stronger winds at higher altitudes).

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. REPOWERING

Simplify permitting for repowering

Permitting for repowering should be simplified, especially for sites that are already licensed, to overcome regulatory barriers and reduce complexity. This could unlock up to 260 GW of additional capacity by 2050 without requiring new land use.

Align repowering strategies

Repowering strategies, in particular where land availability is limited, should be coordinated with grid upgrades and community benefits. This alignment can help reduce environmental impacts while increasing generation efficiency.

2. OFFSHORE FLOATING WIND

Support R&D and cost reduction

Provide targeted support for R&D into environmental impacts, anchoring, and grid integration, alongside mechanisms such as

auctions or IPCEI to bridge the cost gap. These measures can help reduce both the complexity and Levelised Cost of Energy of floating offshore wind, which could supply up to 30% of Europe's electricity needs in a fully decarbonised scenario.

Integrate into marine spatial planning

Incorporate floating offshore wind into marine spatial planning with multi-use solutions to decrease the pressure on marine spatial planning, especially in densely clustered economic activities in coastal areas. Proactive community engagement is essential to secure public support and sustain Europe's global leadership in this field.

3. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY (AWE)

Establish funding and support frameworks

Create AWE-specific R&D funding and remuneration schemes (e.g., CfDs) and invest in complementary technologies and grid infrastructure. Advancing AWE can help manage rising costs and strengthen system reliability, particularly where onshore wind deployment faces constraints.

Develop tailored regulatory frameworks

Introduce permitting and airspace frameworks adapted to AWE, paired with early community engagement, to enable community-led pilots. AWE is particularly suitable for areas with strong wind shear, high-capacity factors, or where traditional turbines face land-use or environmental barriers, including "wind-fatigued" regions.

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LINKS

The interested reader can find more information and project outputs on the project websites :

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Unsplash authors: Werner Soclum,
Анна Читова, Jan Kåre Ness

Other authors: Thomas Schauppenlehner

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